

Third space careers visualised

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This 30-minute presentation recording is based on research involving qualitative questionnaires and semi-structured interviews with those identifying as third space professionals (TSPs) in the United Kingdom, Australia and New Zealand.

Third Space Slowposium: Third Space Careers visualised

Introductions

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McIntosh, E. and Nutt, D. (eds.) (2022) *The Integrated Practitioner in Higher Education: studies in third space professionalism*, Routledge

Blog: [Third Space Perspectives - Exploring Integrated Practice](#)

Watch on YouTube

This presentation showcases a variety of interesting visuals from the study, alongside some of the findings from the interviews, and explores the themes that came out in discussions that related to how participants visualised their career pathways in the third space in higher education. The presentation analyses these findings thematically, demonstrating some key insights into how TSPs describe and then navigate their career pathways in the academy.

About the research: To encourage reflection in the survey and interviews, participants were asked to select and submit up to two images that best described their work in the third space (to the survey), and to visualise their career journey. The images and visualisation were discussed in the participant interviews.

About the authors

<https://www.thirdspaceperspectives.com/>

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